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Abstract

Education and scientific-artistic issues occupy a special place in the work of Muhammad Fuzuli, one of the caliphate artists of medieval Azerbaijani literature, a great master of words, who created works greater than words. The great artist has revealed his stylistic skill by approaching these issues from the general view of the Turkish people with Eastern morality and culture. In the article, these issues that are the basis for Fuzuli's creativity are touched upon, and the issues that have a positive effect on the spiritual world and scientific worldview of young people are discussed. The pure deeds of man, which constitute the main content of Fuzuli's creativity, have always been at the forefront. In the Fuzuli world, humanism and human qualities originate from the Fuzuli philosophy.

The essence of humanism and the perfect human philosophy, which is the basis of Fuzuli's creativity, and its role in educational moments have been investigated. According to the poet, a person can rise to this height with his scientific and high moral qualities. These issues have been widely explored in the poet's work.

Keywords: Azerbaijani literature, upbringing, education, culture, love, work, genre, ghazal

Muhammad Fuzuli is one of the artists who have provided exceptional services to the development of Azerbaijani literature. His creativity is the most valuable spiritual wealth of world culture. The works of the great wordsmith have been a source of inspiration for writing artistic works in many world literatures. In particular, "Divan", which he created in his native language, had a strong influence on the literature of the Turkic peoples. By combining the possibilities of the epic genre with the lyrical genre, he had an important impact on the development of literary thought. In order to express the endless pain and sorrow of ordinary people, Fuzuli turned every word and every verse into a symbol of wisdom and wisdom, and created examples of poetry that have preserved their spiritual value for all times. His poems are a symbol of intelligence and wisdom, an example of figurative thinking and artistic logic.

This year, that is, in 2024, the 530th anniversary of the birth of the contemplative artist Muhammad Fuzuli will be completed. Like other artists, attention and care to Mohammad Fuzuli has always been at a high level. Mr. President Ilham Aliyev, who is loyal to the traditions started by our national leader, signed a decree on January 25, 2024 on the celebration of the 530th anniversary of the birth of Muhammad Fuzuli. The art of Fuzuli is a hearth that takes fire from the language and intelligence of the people and spreads flames, and burns brighter from time to time with the heat of high and holy emotions that have been growing in the human heart for thousands of years [9. p. 25].

All this suggests that Muhammad Fuzuli is a genius wordsmith who has deep roots in Azerbaijani literature, culture and world literature. All genres of classical literature can be seen in the works of Mohammad Fuzuli. Especially, Fuzuli's ghazals glorifying love conquer the hearts of readers. In these ghazals, the tender feelings of a pure, pure heart are expressed. A genius artist by the power of words inspires people to think and dominate their spiritual world.

In his works, love and morality, education and science develop in parallel. Viewing life from the world of Fuzuli is a method of education, because in his works sincere emotions and real life are expressed so fluently that the power of Fuzuli's intelligence speaks for itself

in these works. In his lyrics, folk wisdom and folk love are prominently branched out. In his epic works, one can master the depth of sciences and the secrets of sciences. In the works of Mohammad Fuzuli, the issue of education shows itself prominently. In order to solve these problems, the poet moves allegorical images, penetrates into the issues of life, puts forward important scientific-philosophical, didactic-counseling ideas, that is, by bringing the spiritual and moral qualities of the generation to the fore, he forms his unique aspects. The works of the genius master of words play a very important role in the education of readers.

In each of M. Fuzuli's works, the issues of education and training show themselves prominently. In particular, many types of education prevail in his allegorical works. The basis of the poet's philosophical work is that everything that exists in the world is connected to moral values. The foundation of this morality comes from education and science. According to the artistic and philosophical thought of Muhammad Fuzuli, a person should always be the master and creator of his art. His work "Rindu Zahid" talks about acquiring knowledge, paying attention to good and bad habits in the world, and the role of scientific knowledge about the world. The main idea of the work is the meeting between Zahid father and Rind son, the father's training and admonition to his son, and more precisely, the father's advice to his son, which he knows to be true according to his time.

One of the most important aspects of the work is the prominent promotion of the call to learn knowledge and live hard. With his work Rindü Zahid, the thinker has created an interesting work that reflects his humanistic thoughts about life and people. He suggested in his lyrical works that education and upbringing play an important role in the formation of a person.

Muhammad Fuzuli described the social and political issues of his time in an original way with the work "Bangü Bade", which he wrote in his youth, and touched on social and moral issues in the person of two great rulers. The poem artistically revives the bitter consequences of wars. The events that took place in the assembly of Baden and Bang cause panics and wars.

In the work, the assembly of both Bang and Bade affects people's spirituality. However, unlike Bade,

Bangin's assembly consists of science, poetry and wisdom. Despite this, distrust and immorality prevail in the palaces of both rulers. Both rulers have become prisoners of their feelings. Bade and Bang, who cannot control their feelings, meet. These characters - Bade and Bang - who expose each other's faults, show that drunkenness and dependence on opium will bring great tragedies to human life. With his work "Bangü-Bade", the poet raises issues that protect the moral and spiritual feelings of the new generations and wants to see their future life bright by positively influencing the education of young people.

The great artist revived the social shortcomings he saw in his time in the work "Sohbat ul-asmar". He touched on the futility of unnecessary bragging. In fact, he touched on the social issues of his time in the argument of the fruits, who set themselves on fire by pointing out each other's faults. The poet's work "Sohbat ul-asmar" seems like a simple work at first glance, but it attracts attention with its advice. The allegorical work "Sohbat ul-asmar" is also among the pearls of children's literature. At the same time, this work has a positive effect on the moral and spiritual world of children. Muhammad Fuzuli expressed what he wanted to say and his admirable thoughts in the language of fruits. This work, which is simply interesting, also reflects deep philosophical thoughts.

The great thinker's work "Rindu-zahid" also attracts attention from the point of view of young people's acquisition of science and education, as well as educational issues. The focus has always been on education and learning of young generations. The work "Rindu-zahid" is completely dedicated to these issues. In the work "Rindu-zahid", there are several issues that are important even today and play a key role in human education and personality formation. Today, the influence of the social environment, which plays a major role in the education of young people, is great. In this work of Mohammad Fuzuli, those issues are realistically described.

Don't accumulate too much wealth,
Be prepared to hate your pain. [8. p. 55].

The futility of indulging in worldly goods is poeticized. Every verse of the genius artist suggests that the poet's world of science and morality is a synthesis. He mastered the secrets of many sciences and revealed his scientific potential. Even today, when you read his works again and again, you face a new science. In many cases, Fuzuli is focused on the social-philosophical meaning and purpose of life, on the spirituality of a person.

The works written and created by Muhammad Fuzuli will educate and prepare future generations in the spirit of loyalty to their people, land and most importantly, their homeland.

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